

CLINICAL FEATURES OF COMMUNITY-ACQUIRED PNEUMONIA IN YOUNG CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12503435>

Abstract. *In young children, the increase in infectious morbidity of the bronchopulmonary system directly depends on the influence of risk factors that determine the likelihood of developing pneumonia in young children. Timely identification and elimination of risk factors leads to a reduction in the incidence of respiratory diseases and their complications. In pediatric practice, early and accurate diagnosis of pneumonia and its complications is important.*

Key words: *risk factors, community-acquired pneumonia, young children.*

Actuality. Pneumonia attracts attention due to its prevalence in young children, unfavorable course and outcome, and difficulties of therapy. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), pneumonia is the leading cause of death in children worldwide.[1] Every year, pneumonia kills approximately 1 million children under 5 years of age. In pediatric practice, early and accurate diagnosis of pneumonia and its complications is important. The high incidence of pneumonia occurs at an early age, which is due to the immunological, functional and anatomical immaturity of the body of a child of this age. The study of bronchopulmonary pathology, despite the intensive development of this problem, continues to be relevant for pediatric pulmonology and medicine in general [2,3]. The high frequency and severe course of pneumonia in young children requires the study of developmental risk factors. Research in recent years has established that the most significant factors contributing to the development of pneumonia in young children are: age-related characteristics of the respiratory system, burdened obstetric and perinatal history, immunity characteristics, social factors, environmental factors, allergic history, rickets, nutritional deficiency, anemia, constitutional and metabolic abnormalities, congenital heart defects and lung malformations, primary immune defects, artificial feeding, etc.[4,5]

Clinically, pneumonia is manifested by fever, cough, malaise, and respiratory failure. Atypical pneumonia is characterized by persistent febrile temperature without pronounced manifestations of toxicosis, scanty catarrhal manifestations, conjunctival hyperemia, and auscultatory asymmetry of wheezing [7,8]. Complications of pneumonia include pulmonary (synpneumonic and metapneumonic pleurisy, pulmonary destruction, abscess, pneumothorax and pyopneumothorax) and extrapulmonary (infectious-toxic shock, disseminated intravascular coagulation syndrome, cardiovascular failure, respiratory distress syndrome).[6]

Purpose of the study. Study of risk factors and features of the course of community-acquired pneumonia in young children.

Materials and methods. In accordance with the objectives, a survey of 45 children from 1 year to 3 years was carried out. Of these, 20 (44.4%) are girls, 25 (55.6%) are boys.

The studies were carried out in the department of the City Children's Clinical Hospital No. 1, Tashkent. In all patients, anamnestic, clinical, and laboratory studies were studied, as well as the identification of modifying risk factors to determine their prognostic value for the development of pneumonia.

Results. Based on this goal, we studied the course and main risk factors influencing the development of complicated pneumonia in young children. The clinical picture of pneumonia was characterized by the main clinical symptoms, such as: shortness of breath (an increase in the

number of breaths from 40 per 1 min) 30 (66.7%), all patients had an increase in body temperature for more than three days and signs of intoxication - poor appetite, weakness, malaise, anxiety; pallor of the skin, signs of cyanosis were found in 23 (51.1%) patients, and the predominant involvement of additional muscles in breathing was also determined. The cough at the beginning of the disease was dry, and then became wet. Other catarrhal symptoms: rhinitis, pharyngitis, conjunctivitis were observed in 19 (43.3%) patients. In 35 (77.8%) patients, pneumonia proceeded without complications, i.e. Respiratory failure, cardiorespiratory syndrome, toxicosis, and infectious-toxic shock were not observed. During an objective examination, shortening of the percussion sound and weakening of breathing were observed in 72% of children with uncomplicated pneumonia, and harsh breathing was observed in 94% of those examined. The presence of moist fine bubbling rales was noted in 44% of children, medium bubbling rales – in 22% of patients, crepitus – in 17% of patients. A combination of local percussion and auscultation symptoms was recorded in 70% of those examined. In the hemogram in the first three days of uncomplicated pneumonia, leukocytosis was recorded in 56.6% of cases, neutrophilia - in 43.2% of children, leukopenia - in 15.1% of children, lymphocytosis - in 8.8% of those examined. An increase in ESR was detected in 66% of those examined, mild anemia was detected in 42.2% of patients.

When studying the risk factors for the development of pneumonia, most patients had a variety of concomitant pathologies, which undoubtedly aggravated the severity of the disease and influenced the duration of persistence of the infection.

When studying the premorbid background, rickets was observed in 8(17,85)% (including 6.7% of patients, Harrison’s fissure and “companion’s breasts” were detected), 19 (42.2%) of the examined patients were diagnosed with anemia (including II degree - in 5%), protein-energy deficiency - 1; -2 SD (PED) - in 17.7%, neurological diseases (convulsions, PPPNS) - in 6 (13.3%), exudative catarrhal diathesis (ECD) and food allergies in 6 (13.35)% and this instilled a tendency for a protracted course and broncho-obstructive complications. 22% of patients had a combination of 2-3 underlying diseases, 65% of patients belonged to the group of frequent ARI patients. In 16% of patients, x-rays revealed thymic hyperplasia, which is a risk factor for severe pneumonia and a tendency to a protracted course. An assessment of the nature of feeding in children in the first year of life showed that, on average, children were breastfed for 4-1.1 months.

Conclusions. In the formation of a complicated course of pneumonia in children of the first year of life the determining role belongs to factors of the ante-, intra-, and neonatal periods. Among the risk factors for severe complicated pneumonia, factors that form an unfavorable premorbid background and immunosuppressive state in children, especially infants (unfavorable course of pregnancy and childbirth in mothers, prematurity, nutritional deficiency, anemia in mothers)

currently come to the fore. The most significant clinical criteria for the complicated course of pneumonia are identified: microcirculatory disorders, bilateral weakening of breathing during auscultation, central nervous system depression syndrome, respiratory rate more than 60 per minute, abdominal bloating, focal-confluent form of pneumonia during radiography of children).

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